

INVESTIGATION OF THE PHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF FIRE-RESISTANT MATERIALS BASED ON COTTON AND BASALT FIBERS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the physical and mechanical properties of fire-resistant materials. The study examined samples of fire-resistant materials made from cotton and basalt fibers for strength, abrasion resistance, elongation at break, stretching under stress lower than the breaking load, resistance to single and repeated stretching, wrinkling, and tearing. Based on the experimental results, their heat resistance and resistance to thermal shock were analyzed. The obtained data were used to develop recommendations for improving the production processes of fire-resistant materials. The findings have practical significance for metallurgy, the chemical industry, and the manufacturing of heat-resistant equipment.

Keywords: Fire-resistant materials, local raw materials, cotton, basalt, physical-mechanical strength, air permeability, abrasion resistance, elongation at break, stretchability, wrinkling resistance, tear resistance.

At present, the production of fire-resistant materials remains one of the most pressing issues in our country. The transition of textile industry management to a cluster system, deep processing of local raw materials, proper utilization of new equipment and technologies, and reduction of raw material consumption are among the factors contributing to this problem. These factors inevitably pose challenges for the textile industry, particularly in the creation of new types of fire-resistant materials and the expansion of product assortments.

This creates a demand for the production of new types of fire-resistant materials with high-quality performance and low raw material consumption.

The physicommechanical properties of fire-resistant materials serve as descriptors that define the limits of their practical use.

Among the indicators characterizing the physicommechanical properties of fire-resistant materials, the following were adopted: strength, abrasion resistance, elongation at break, stretching under stress lower than the breaking force, resistance to single and repeated stretching, resistance to wrinkling and tearing, and dimensional stability under hot and humid conditions.

Depending on the intended conditions of use and functional purpose, specific indicators were selected to describe the structure and physicommechanical properties of fire-resistant materials.

Based on the analysis of the aforementioned data, scientific research was conducted to study the effect of changes in the weave of fire-resistant materials on the physicommechanical properties of the fabric.

The physicommechanical properties of fire-resistant materials were experimentally tested in the laboratory of the "Testing and Certification Center" at Namangan State University of Technology, and the obtained results are presented in Table 3.

One of the main indicators of fire-resistant fabrics is tensile strength and elongation at break. All GOST standards applied to fire-resistant fabrics include normative values for elongation at break and tensile strength. Tensile strength is defined as the force required to stretch a fabric sample measuring 20 cm × 5 cm using a testing device, where the sample first elongates and then breaks under the applied load. Tensile strength is expressed in Newtons (N). The tensile strength of the presented samples was determined using the standard method with a "YG-026T" dynamometer.

Analysis of the tensile strength results of the new fire-resistant material showed that, for the warp direction, the tensile strength of the fire-resistant material was 157 N for Sample I, 116 N for Sample II, 139 N for Sample III, 114 N for Sample IV, 112 N for Sample V, 156 N for Sample VI, 139 N for Sample VII, 164 N for Sample VIII, 174 N for Sample IX, and 144 N for Sample X. For the weft direction, the tensile strength was 344 N for Sample I, 514 N for Sample II, 1088 N for Sample III, 441 N for Sample IV, 420 N for Sample V, 548 N for Sample VI, 822 N for Sample VII, 911 N for Sample VIII, 775 N for Sample IX, and 1088 N for Sample X. The analysis indicates that among the ten Samples tested, the highest tensile strength in the warp direction was observed in Sample IX, while in the weft direction it was highest in Sample X. (1-rasm).

Figure 1. Tensile strength of the materials

The elongation of refractory fabrics is defined as their extension at the point of rupture under an applied force. The elongation is characterized by the increase in length of the specimen being tested. The extension at rupture can be expressed in absolute or relative terms. When refractory fabrics with a clamped (gauge) length of 100 mm are tested, their absolute and relative elongation values are numerically equal.

The analysis of the tensile elongation properties of refractory raw materials up to the point of rupture showed that, for the new range of materials, the elongation of the warp direction of the refractory raw material was 31.0% for Sample I, 34.5% for Sample II, 31.9% for Sample III, 44.9% for Sample IV, 31.0% for Sample V, 31.0% for Sample VI, 34.5% for Sample VII, 32.9% for Sample VIII, 46.9% for Sample IX, and 31.0% for Sample X. The elongation of the fabric in the weft direction up to rupture was 8.6% for Sample I, 4.9% for Sample II, 6.5% for Sample III, 8.1% for Sample IV, 8.6% for Sample V, 8.8% for Sample VI, 5.9% for Sample VII, 6.8% for Sample VIII, 8.8% for Sample IX, and 8.9% for Sample X. Based on the analysis results, it was determined that among the ten tested samples, the refractory material exhibited the highest elongation at break in the warp direction for Sample IX and in the weft direction for Sample X (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Variation in elongation at break of fire-resistant fabrics

Among the obtained refractory materials, Samples VI and IX demonstrated the highest abrasion resistance. The abrasion resistance of Sample VI was 75,000 cycles, while that of Sample IX was 74,000 cycles. It was found that the abrasion resistance of Sample II was 15,000 cycles lower than that of Sample VI (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Abrasion resistance of the materials

In conclusion, the analysis of the physical and mechanical properties of the above-mentioned refractory fabrics revealed that modifications in the structure of refractory materials have a positive effect on the air permeability, strength, elongation, and abrasion resistance of the fabrics.

Using cotton yarns in the warp direction and basalt yarns in the weft direction alters the fabric structure and enables the production of refractory

materials with improved hygienic and shape-retention properties, as well as enhanced aesthetic appearance.

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